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A comparative multi-case study investigating leadership for inclusion and social justice through collaborative professionalism in two primary mainstream schools in Greece and England.

Abstract

The literature in the field of education advocates that the heart of inclusive education is collaboration. This qualitative comparative multi case study investigated the role of school leadership in promoting inclusive education and social justice in Greece and England through the lens of Collaborative Professionalism (CP). It focused on whether CP was enacted, by whom and its relation to inclusion and social justice. It attempted to share information about both countries with a view to positively influencing one another. One of the aims was to help construct a map which would include important information about inclusive education in two countries as part of a bigger worldwide map. Emerging findings suggest that rejecting authoritarian approaches that leave little or no space for teacher initiative play a crucial role in promoting an inclusive ethos. Additionally, including school community members and students in the inclusive education process while building collaboration across schools and systems could lead to more inclusive practices and a more just society. The decentralised educational system, contrary to a centralised one, offered more opportunities to school leaders to initiate the creation of inclusive cultures and promote social justice. A key finding of communication played a significant role on this and as such will be the focus of this paper.

Keywords

Leadership, Communication, Inclusive Education, Collaborative Professionalism, Social Justice, Comparative study

3 Main Highlights

1. The style of leadership and the structure of the educational system plays an important role in the promotion and enactment of inclusion and social justice. The centralised system in Greece appears to allow very little space for teacher collaboration in contrast to the English school where collaborative practices were encouraged and promoted by the school leaders.
2. In the Greek context, there appeared to be a lack of common ethos and goals, as evidenced by teachers having mixed views on understanding inclusion and social justice. In contrast to the English school, there was an agreed understanding on inclusion and social justice.
3. The Greek centralised educational system in contrast to the English one seemed to allow very little space for teacher initiative for inclusive practices. One system could benefit from the other and result into more inclusive practices and improved policies.

Introduction

This paper will include a short presentation of the research topic, the rationale, the pertinent literature, the research context, problem and questions, the methodology, the key findings, and the contribution to knowledge.

Research Rationale

Inclusion demands asking what kind of world we want to live in, what kind of skills and commitment people need to coexist and develop in a diverse society and it explores how we can create a world that accepts all differences (Sapon-Shevin, 2003). A socially just society is parallel to inclusion. They both address and eliminate marginalisation, poverty, and racism. Both Greece (in 2012) and England (in 2009) have agreed to the UNCRPD and its conditions. Both countries theoretically have agreed to the vision of inclusion and social justice, but in

practice there seems to be a gap. There are many ways to approach inclusion, but this study adopted a specific lens to it, Collaborative Professionalism (CP).

CP is about collaborative enquiry, action, and collaborative responsibility (Hargreaves, 2019). Its goal is to provide the best possible education and school life conditions for all students. Central to inclusion and social justice is leadership which is closely intertwined with school improvement and the quality of school experience inside and outside school for the students (Spillane and Diamond, 2007; Angelides, Antoniou and Charalambous, 2010). The term leadership is a debatable term. It is not about giving instruction to co-workers (Male and Palaiologou, 2012). In the context of inclusion, it is about guiding and modelling collaboration that is central to inclusive practices (Ainscow and Sandill, 2010; MacRuairc, 2016). Although there is a plethora of data and knowledge around leadership and collaborative practices for inclusion, there seems to be a gap between theory and reality (Messiou, 2016) that this study has investigated.

Support in Greek mainstream schools, according to the latest law 4547 (Law 4547/2018), is either provided by the parallel support teacher in the mainstream classroom or by attending a different classroom (Special Education Needs Provision within Mainstream Education - Eurydice - European Commission, 2021), the inclusive classroom, for specific hours per week. In English schools (Children and Families Act, Special Educational Needs and Disability Code of Practice) (GOV.UK, 2014) the support includes the involvement of local authorities, parents, and students in the school community. The goal of the latter school is to create an opportunity for a better and more effective collaboration of all stakeholders to support the students. However, policies alone, without the guidance of effective leaders do not help create and sustain effective inclusive and socially just cultures (Robinson, 2010). Evidence from literature demonstrated that the success of inclusion is directly linked to the style of leadership (Leithwood, Harris and Hopkins, 2008) which ought to be collaborative. However, there are

numerous issues, such as a lack of opportunities for teachers to become leaders themselves, a lack of teacher training, a non-inclusive curriculum, a lack of planning time and time for sharing expertise and liaising with staff and the wider community. All these issues hinder the creation of those inclusive cultures in schools. This paper draws upon a doctoral thesis that explored the ten tenets of CP (Hargreaves, 2019) as a means of supporting collaborative inclusive cultures.

The four basic concepts of this study related to the ten tenets (Figure 1); *Leadership, CP, inclusion, social justice* (Figure 2). The research questions and interview questions for the participants were also formed based on the ten tenets as was data analysis. The enactment of collaborative practices was identified in the schools, by using the ten tenets. The ten tenets were also used to explore the leader`s practices and views on inclusion and the impact they had in the school life of the students in relation to the school community and wider society. The ten tenets are outlined in Figure 1 below and the connection of the four basic concepts for this study can be understood better from Figure 2.

Figure 1, Ten Tenets of CP

Figure 2, The Four Basic Concepts of the Study

Integration and inclusion

In Greek settings, the concept of integration was introduced around 1990 to influence and

change past perceptions of students with special educational needs that were considered “*lazy*” or “*naughty*”. Greece was following the European trend of inclusion, which was considered as a `panacea that would resolve` the stigmatisation and marginalisation of people with disabilities. However, this policy-borrowing from Europe caused confusion both theoretically and in practice as this philosophy was borrowed from other educational systems (Zoniou-Sideri, 2004). The inclusion of students with SEN (Special Educational Needs) is closely connected with human rights and positive social change in socially just societies (Angelle and Torrance, 2019). That is why social justice needs to be deeper investigated.

Social Justice and Biopsychosocial model of disability

Despite the different uses, social justice, when referred to education, is about `benefiting` the least advantaged students (Bringhouse, 2009) by challenging the current education systems, structures and dynamics that have led to power inequalities and phenomena of exclusion. The model of disability that seemed to create space for human rights and brought new perspective as to what is considered disability was the Biopsychosocial model of disability.

This model “*drew on biological, psychological and social perspectives*” and brought possible new factors as to what was viewed as disability in education (Farrell, 2009, p. 30). The bio part of this model linked with what the person with disabilities was able, or capable of doing according to Nussbaum (2011), and how the rights of this person were respected or catered for. Students do not enter an institution based on equal opportunities (King and Travers, 2017). The upper goal of leadership practice should be the recognition and elimination of those by increasing the awareness of the sociological and sociocultural aspects of schools for equal opportunities (King and Travers, 2017). The process towards social justice and inclusion requires people, and specifically leaders, who understand and stand next to the students with disabilities and recognise their rights (Choules, 2007; Evans, 2007). That is why it is important to have a shared leadership that supports this vision.

Distributed leadership

Distributed leadership is viewed as a shift from individual to shared leadership (Orphanos and Orr, 2014) and is arguably the preferred model of leadership in many countries. Successful head teachers recognise the limitations of a singular leadership approach and adopt a form of leadership “*distributed through collaborative and joint working*” (Harris, 2004, p. 16).

It is of vital importance that the school leaders believe in the idea of inclusion in order to pass it along to others. Therefore, it should be a leader’s duty to set the values and vision of inclusion and social justice as a priority. It is significant to provide staff with opportunities for communication as part of the collaboration (Ní Bhroin and King, 2019). School leaders are in a unique position to influence collaboration among teachers and other stakeholders. However, they may not be equipped to perform this role suitably (Balyer, Karatas and Alci, 2015). This paper explores leadership for inclusion in two different contexts.

Research questions

Consistent with the aims of the study, the following research questions were posed for investigation:

- How do school leaders in mainstream primary schools in Greece and England currently understand and enact inclusion?
- To what extent do school leaders promote inclusive practice in mainstream primary schools in Greece and England?
- To what extent are collaborative practices evident in supporting inclusion and social justice in Greece and England?
- How do parents and students with SEN understand and practise inclusion and social justice in mainstream schools in Greece and England?

Aim/Significance of the study

This study aimed to explore and compare the understanding and enactment of inclusive education in Greece and England. It attempted to analyse how inclusion and social justice are promoted by leadership and what collaborative practices happen to support that. Comparative studies tend to create more debate between countries and therefore enhance the dialogue for improving policies (Booth and Ainscow, 1998), while at the same time this may lead to a better understanding of one's own system (Crossley and Broadfoot, 1992). Exploring the commitment and enactment of inclusion in these different contexts will arguably support the international call for collaborative approaches to inclusive practice (Ainscow and Sandill, 2010).

Bronfenbrenner's (1979) ecological concept views school as a microsystem embedded within a macro-regional or national education system. This study gave the opportunity to school leaders and other staff members to reflect as individuals and as teams and talk about topics related to inclusive education and to review the school's ethos and policies. It also investigated the dialogue, the research relationship between Greece and England. One country could become a role model for the other. The goal of this is for both countries to influence their educational systems positively, learn from each other and work towards better practices in different settings (Pfeffer, 2015). The findings and recommendations of this study are expected to create an international map which, based on the conclusions about leadership for inclusion and social justice through CP, could provide a strong basis for future reference and improvement on the topic. Additionally, gaps in terms of CP and inclusion could be covered, resulting possibly in policy changing. This could draw more attention to creating collaborative and inclusive cultures in schools. The comparative nature of the study played a major part in the structure of the whole methodology.

Methodology

Philosophical assumptions

An interpretivist/ relativist ontological stance was adopted for this research as it focused on interviewing participants and gathering data from people's perspectives, their perceptions were considered subjective and personal. This aligned with the epistemological assumption that recognises that knowledge is a construct of people's perspectives (Constructionism). The aim was to 'describe and translate' the subject from the perspective and experiences of all participants. This enhanced the triangulation of the data which also raised the trustworthiness of the study.

Research design

A qualitative approach to research aligned with the philosophical stance as outlined above. In order to achieve the comparison, a case study and comparative design were selected (Bryman, 2012).

Case studies help investigate a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context and in which multiple sources of evidence are used for a more truthful and clear result (Yin, 2011). In this specific study, the voices of the school leaders and staff members, parents and students constructed the reality. The focus of the comparison was to unearth and explore the historical and contemporary processes that have produced a sense of shared place, goal or identity to the topic investigated (Bartlett and Vavrus, 2017). The Greek system has always been a strictly centralised system that allowed very little space for school leaders to initiate change, while in England, schools seem to have a relative freedom regarding managing their finances and school policy allowing them to act as independent units.

Methods and sampling

47 participants took part in this study comprising of teachers, school leaders, parents who have children with SEN and primary students with SEN. Data collection methods included semi-structured interviews, observations, visual methods and sociograms.

This study adopted the non-probability method for sampling (Cohen et al., 2011). The research site in England was identified when I was working there as a staff member for a few years. After I left, I kept in touch with the school leaders and a few other colleagues. Most of the staff members were different when I collected the data. Similarly with the Greek school, I chose it as it had the reputation of an inclusive school as it was the only school in the area that had two inclusive classrooms. I contacted the head teacher at each school via email first, I shared my plan and ideas with them about the research and they were open to participation. All participants were given a Plain Language Statement to be informed about the research aims and give their approval.

Positionality

“All writing is positioned” and *“within a stance”* (Creswell, 2007, p. 179). Taking into consideration the above, I thought of myself as an insider, and I chose to explore the pros and cons of “insiderness”. In my study I engaged in less intimate insider research, as it had been four years since I left the English school and many more since I left Greece. In my study the long absence from both educational settings and the lack of contact with most interviewees, created a gap in the relations with the participants and has worked in my favour regarding the bias of participants having formed preconceptions about me and the study. This approach matched my constructionist stance where I wanted the participants to build their own reality based on their experiences and opinions.

Ethical considerations

The first step to start the process of data collection was to gain ethical approval from DCU

and consent from the English school and the Greek school. The whole procedure began in January 2018 and lasted more than three months. As for the interviews with students, I had prioritised using a child friendly language and visual methods for students with speech, language, and communication difficulties. Parental consent was also a priority when interviewing students. Also, the literature review and the pilot phase helped with clarifying the inclusion and exclusion criteria that I had to keep in mind when interviewing or observing during data collection. Ethical review procedures were followed, starting with the explanation, and signing of the consent form. The interviews began by stating the participants right to withdraw from the study at any point without any change in the way they would be treated or any other adverse consequences (Cohen et al., 2011) Also, it was clarified that no personal data that would reveal the participant`s identity would be shared (Robson, 2011). Anonymity was also prioritised, and pseudonyms were used.

Data analysis

For the data analysis NVivo R was used. The interpretation of the data was done exclusively by the researcher. Thematic analysis was employed for this study. It involved identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The key categories mainly derived from the comparison of the two countries, similarities, and differences in data from the Greek and English schools. After the completion of the coding, the codes were merged into broader themes and sub-themes that later were reviewed and refined (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Emerging findings

This section presents an analysis of the data collected so far regarding the role of school leadership in promoting inclusion and social justice in the two mainstream primary schools in Greece and England.

Three emerging themes were identified: *Understanding and interpreting the terms Inclusion and Social Justice, CP and Leadership practices and responsibilities*. This paper will only focus on the most prominent sub-theme ‘Communication’, that emerged under the CP theme.

Communication

Effective communication was deemed the most prominent sub-theme in the analysis. In the English school, the deputy head highlighted the importance of having an inclusive ethos and vision in place. She spoke of an inclusive culture that the head must put in place for all staff.

“If the head does not have that vision and buying into it and holding on to it at all times, then it will fall apart”. She continued:

I mean everything starts from the head teacher ultimately...I mean we got a leadership team where there is a lot of shared responsibility....and that is really important so ultimately if the head doesn't have that ethos, everything else falls down.

She highlighted that staff worked together “as a collective” towards achieving an inclusive ethos and this was obvious as there would always be someone there to support them in case, they needed it. Parallel to that, most of the participants spoke of a nice welcoming feeling when entering the school that made students feel comfortable and safe to share information and open up and that was considered an indicator of inclusion. Display boards and school art exhibits confirmed the atmosphere (see Figure 3 Playtime Charter and 4 Playtime Rules below).

Figure 3, Playtime Charter

Figure 4, Playtime Rules

In Greek settings on the other hand, several class teachers thought that the school was open and welcoming to students with SEN “*because that's the way the school functioned all those years,*” (SEN teacher) meaning that it was a culture that teachers carried on naturally through the years. There was no other communication, no visual evidence or official guidance from the Ministry of Education or the school leaders as in the English school. There were also no display boards with children's work to communicate an inclusive ethos. Most of the teachers and parents thought that there was a positive atmosphere and staff had a welcoming stance towards students with SEN, without necessarily giving specific examples or evidence. Interestingly, there was a class teacher who had an opposite view. Specifically, he believed that due to the centralised and bureaucratic nature of the Greek educational system, there would be no other option for the teachers. He said that “*if teachers could avoid it [having students with SEN in their classroom], they would*”. As he said, “*surely, no teacher would want to have them in their class, when there is the SEN class. It just makes their life more difficult*”. Another class teacher believed that including a student in a mainstream classroom depended on the personality and the views of each teacher. He stated, “*for example, it would depend on whether a student was a foreigner and whether the teacher didn't like foreigners*” then the teacher may not want to include those students. He also reported that they felt secure and free to open up to their teachers to share their struggles. Parents from their side felt that there was an inclusive vision and atmosphere in the school. Specifically, a mother of a student with SEN said that “*in that school there was a non-written rule of responsibility, egalitarianism and equity*”.

Contributions (so far)

At the heart of inclusion lies collaboration (Florian, 2017). It is of crucial importance that teachers cooperate and share information, as no profession can progress effectively without it. Having common goals, vision and ethos enhances the communication between stakeholders and therefore helps the inclusion of students. In this study, findings suggest that school staff

from the English school had set the promotion of the inclusive ethos and social justice as their priority. Staff and parents felt that there was an inclusive atmosphere right from entering the school. Feeling welcomed and having an open-door policy communicated to them strengthened the inclusive culture. This also signalled the enactment of the 8th tenet of CP (Common meaning and purpose). The analysis also suggested that communication was enhanced in the English school as there were scheduled time periods for collaboration, professional development, and meetings with parents. In the Greek school, class teachers had mixed views on how welcoming and supportive the school was with students with SEN, showing that there were not clear goals and no vision communicated for the staff members to commit to. According to the participants, there was no official guidance from the Ministry of Education in terms of inclusion and social justice, no clear roles and responsibilities given to staff members. Despite policies mandating inclusion, it seemed that opportunities for collaboration and communication were not happening, therefore affecting the inclusion of the students with SEN. Most of the classrooms and corridors seemed empty of students' work. The centralised nature of the Greek educational system allowed very little space for initiative for inclusive practices and the responsible people from the Ministry of Education seemed to have forgotten to communicate with the schools and to update the related inclusion policies. Interestingly, if there were teachers who responsibly tried to include students with SEN in their classroom, inclusion seemed to happen accidentally and not in an organised and supportive manner. That signalled gaps in the communication with the staff. There was no designated scheduled time for grade level meetings or professional development. The lack of common vision and SEN awareness in the Greek school, along with the reported lack of permanent staff has probably resulted in the plethora of views and behaviours in terms of creating and sustaining a welcoming feeling in the school, therefore affecting the communication with the stakeholders and the inclusion of the students with SEN. This study's emerging results provide some insights into two different educational systems

understandings and practices of inclusion and social justice, both highlighting a key role for communication. Placing communication as a priority for policy makers, head teachers and teachers alike is essential for developing and sustaining inclusive practices in schools and society.

Suggestions for application and for further research

Given the appropriate consent from the Ministry of Education, future research directions could explore a research design/framework that gives more autonomy to the school leaders in Greek schools to create and strengthen an inclusive ethos and culture. The issue of creating and sustaining inclusive cultures is central to the success for all students. Time and space for professional learning could be the solution for creating those inclusive cultures. Communication at and between the micro, meso, and macro levels of the system could enhance understandings and practice of inclusive education and social justice. A less centralised, more autonomous educational system where teachers would be trusted to take more action, expand the network, and communicate more easily could result in a more inclusive and socially just school reality.

Conclusion

The key emerging findings so far suggested that a centralised educational system that allows little space for school leaders to initiate change, can lead to limited opportunities for communication and collaboration for the inclusion of students with SEN. On the contrary, common goals and ethos in education seems to enhance the communication of the staff members with each other, students, and parents as they develop a sense of belonging and responsibility working towards the same goals.

References

- Ainscow, M. and Sandill, A. (2010) 'Developing inclusive education systems: the role of organisational cultures and leadership', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 14(4), pp. 401-416.
- Angelides, P., Antoniou, E. and Charalambous, C. (2010) 'Making sense of inclusion for leadership and schooling: a case study from Cyprus' *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 13(3), pp. 319-334.
- Angelle, P.S. and Torrance, D. (2019) *Cultures of social justice leadership: an intercultural context of schools*, Cham, Switzerland: Springer
- Balyer, A., Karatas, H. and Alci, B. (2015) 'School Principals' Roles in Establishing Collaborative Professional Learning Communities at Schools' *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 197, pp. 1340-1347.
- Bartlett, L., and Vavrus, F. (2017) 'Comparative case studies: an innovative approach'. *Nordic Journal of Comparative and International Education (NJCIE)*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.7577/njcie.1929>
- Booth, T., and Ainscow, M. (1998) *From them to us: An international study of inclusion in education*, London: Routledge.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006) 'Using thematic analysis in psychology', *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3, 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Bringhouse, H. (2009) 'Educational Equality and School Reform', In *Educational Equality*, edited by G. Haydon, 15–68. London: Continuum.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979) *The ecology of human development: experiments by nature and design*. Cambridge, MA, Harvard University Press.
- Bryman, A. (2012). 'Social Research Methods' 4th Edition, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Choules, K. (2007) 'Shifting sands of social justice discourse: From situating the problem with "them" to situating it with "us"', *Review of Education, Pedagogy, and Cultural Studies*, 29, pp. 461-481.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2011) *Research methods in education*. 7th edn. Milton Park, Oxon: Routledge.
- Creswell, J.W. (2007). *Qualitative Inquiry & Research Design*. 2nd edition, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Crossley, M. and Broadfoot, P. (1992) 'Comparative and International Research in Education: scope, problems and potential', *British Educational Research Journal*, 18 (2), pp. 104-114.

Eurydice - European Commission. (2021) '*Special Education Needs Provision within Mainstream Education*' - Eurydice - European Commission. [online] Available at: https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/eurydice/content/special-education-needs-provision-within-mainstream-education-27_en (Accessed: 4 May 2019).

Evans, A. E., (2007) 'Horton, Highlander, and leadership education: Lessons for preparing educational leaders for social justice', *Journal of School Leadership*, 17, 250-275.

Farrell, M. (2009) '*Foundations of special education: An introduction*'. Wiley-Blackwell, 2009, 313 pp, ISBN: 978 0 470 75396 5 (hbk) 978 0 470 75397 2 (pbk).

Florian, L. (2005) 'Inclusive practice: what, why and how?' In Topping, K. & Maloney, S, (eds.), *The RoutledgeFalmer reader in inclusive education*, pp. 29-40. Abington: RoutledgeFalmer.

Florian, L. (2017) "The Heart of Inclusive Education is Collaboration", *Pedagogika*, 126(2), pp. 248–253. doi: 10.15823/p.2017.32.

GOV.UK. (2014) *Landmark Children and Families Act 2014 gains royal assent*. Online. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/landmark-children-and-families-act-2014-gains-royal-assent> (Accessed: 14 June 2020).

Griffiths, G. (1985) *Doubts, dilemmas and diary-keeping: some reflections on teacher-based research*, in R. Burgess (Ed.) *Issues in educational research: qualitative methods*. London: The Falmer Press.

Hargreaves, A. (2019) 'Teacher collaboration: 30 years of research on its nature, forms, limitations and effects', *Teachers and Teaching*, 25 (5), pp. 603-621.

Harris, A. (2004) Distributed leadership and school improvement. *Educational Management Administration and Leadership*, 32, 11-24.

King, F., & Travers, J. (2017) Social justice leadership through the lens of ecological systems theory In P. Angelle (Ed). *A Global Perspective of Social Justice Leadership for School Principals* (pp. 147-165) Charlotte, NC, USA: Information Age Publishing.

Leithwood, K., Harris, A. and Hopkins, D. (2008) 'Seven strong claims about successful school leadership', *School Leadership & Management*, 28(1), pp. 27-42.

MacRuairc, G. (2016) *Leadership for inclusive schools* [Webinar]. In Teaching Council Research Webinars. Retrieved from <http://www.teachingcouncil.ie/en/Research/Research-Webinars/Leadership-for-Inclusive-Schools/>

Male, T. and Palaiologou, I. (2012) 'Learning-centred leadership or pedagogical leadership? An alternative approach to leadership in education contexts'. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 15(1), pp. 107-118.

- Marshall, M. N. (1996) 'Sampling for qualitative research'. *Family Practice*. 13(6):522-525. (available at: <http://fampra.oxfordjournals.org/content/13/6/522.full.pdf> [accessed 21st November 2019])
- Messiou, K. (2016) Research in the field of inclusive education: time for a rethink? *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, DOI: 10.1080/13603116.2016.1223184.
- Ní Bhroin, Ó, & King, F. (2019) 'Teacher education for inclusive education: a framework for developing collaboration for the inclusion of students with support plans'. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(1), pp. 38-63.
- Nussbaum, M. C. (2011) Capabilities, Entitlements, Rights: Supplementation and Critique. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 12(1), pp. 23–37.
- Orphanos, S., & Orr, M. T. (2014) Learning leadership matters: The influence of innovative school leadership preparation on teachers' experiences and outcomes. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 42(5), 680–700. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143213502187>
- Pfeffer F. T. (2015) Equality and quality in education. A comparative study of 19 countries. *Social science research*, 51, 350–368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2014.09.004>
- Robinson, V. (2010) *From Instructional Leadership to Leadership Capabilities: Empirical Findings and Methodological Challenges*. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 9(1), pp. 1-26.
- Robson, C. (2011) *Real world research*. 3rd edn. Oxford: Wiley Publications.
- Sapon-Shevin, M. (2003) *Inclusion: A matter of social justice*. *Educational Leadership*, 61(2), 25–28.
- Spillane, J. and Diamond, J. (2007) *Distributed leadership in practice*. New York: Teachers College, Columbia University.
- Stake, R. E. (1995). *The art of case study research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Yin, R. (2011) *Qualitative Research from start to finish*. New York: The Guildford Press.
- Zoniou-Sideri, A. (2004) *Contemporary Accession Approaches*. Ellinika Grammata, Athens.